

FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL PROFICIENCY OF TEACHERS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION IN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: In this article factors of development of pedagogical proficiency of teachers of the primary education are stated.

Аннотация: В данной статье изложены факторы развития педагогического мастерства учителей начальных классов.

Key words: Pedagogical proficiency, pedagogical process, national program of personnel training, pedagogical capability, pedagogical technique, pedagogical method.

It is considered that it is essential to develop pedagogical proficiency of teachers of primary education for society. Educating young generation who is future of independent Uzbekistan is sensitive and controversial issue and it demands quite a lot of attention. Teachers who have pedagogical knowledge and proficiency must know methodological basics of pedagogy, factors and rules of personal development, essence of national program of personnel training and its aims and problem. "National program of personnel training" lodges ideas of general and vocational culture, social activity, finding right way in social and political sphere, formation of the next generation who is able to solve important problems, perfect and settled to society, acquired educational and professional program. What is more it conveys ideas of educating high-powered citizens. One of the qualities of modern teacher is loyalty for his job, conviction for ideas, love of his/her profession. These qualities differentiate teachers from other professions. Course of pedagogical proficiency conveys pedagogical culture and practice, history of pedagogical opinions, skills of teachers, pedagogical and communicative capability of teachers, psychology and culture of communication, pedagogical ethics, pedagogical technology and ways of acquisition of it, speech culture, capacity of teacher during the process of teaching

and educating, academic organization of teachers' work, self-development of teachers, issues of prevalence of advanced pedagogical experience. Some of important of pedagogical technique are communicative skills of teachers, right and clear expression of ideas. Capability of teachers might improve if they demonstrate following qualities. They are didactic, academic, perceptive, communicative, organizer and paying his/her attention. Methods which we use during the lessons help students to improve their knowledge and form teachers' proficiency. Hundred years ago, great Uzbek scholar Abdulla Avlani said: "Education is issue which is either life or death, either hope or catastrophe, either blessing or disaster." This aphorism is valuable in present days. Education is essential to keep up with advanced world indeed. Many eastern scholars and philosophers noted skills of teachers, tradition of teacher-student in their scientific heritage. For instance, well-known scholar and philosopher Abu Nasr Farabi (873-930) claimed: "Teachers must not oppress their their students. Also they must not indulge them." Because too much oppression causes hatred, and also too much indulgence creates contempt. Farabi advised to use 'hard' and 'soft' way during the lesson according to children's behavior. Famous scientist Zyazyun enumerated components of pedagogical skills of teachers.

- a) Humanitarian tendency of teachers' life (their interests, positive position on their profession, ideals)
- b) Professional knowledge (knowledge about which related to their job and subject, methodology, pedagogy and psychology.)
- c) Pedagogical capability (ability of familiarity, explanation, observant, having a good reputation, equal treatment to everyone, looking to the future with confidence, paying attention to everyone, and pedagogical norms)

d) Pedagogical technique (speech, mime and control of emotion)

Therefore, whole system of pedagogical proficiency consists of following components: Having humanitarian tendency of pedagogue. Their interests, conviction and ideals should be aimed to educate perfect generation. Having knowledge about subjects, teaching methods, pedagogics and psychology; Having pedagogical proficiency (communicative skills, efficiency, looking to the future with confidence, professional independence, understanding any information quickly); Mastering pedagogical technique (ability of self-control and cooperation).

So, concept of pedagogical proficiency consists of several components which related to each other. In this case, pedagogical proficiency is thought as 'pedagogical system' and it is described like this: 'Pedagogical proficiency is complex of personal qualities and independent formation of effective pedagogical-psychological work. It means that teacher has reached his/her high level' Therefore, pedagogical proficiency is to organize all kind of his work conveniently and effectively, to use them for personal development and achievement, to form students' outlook and efficiency.[6] Every teacher has pedagogical skills to be successful must be. The main principle of pedagogical skill is low labor consumption and achieve great results. Creativity is always his companion will be Pedagogical skills are formed only in a capable, talented person who is interested in pedagogical activity. Pedagogical activity it has a creative character in its essence. Teacher student identity forms, makes independent decisions in unexpected situation does, solves pedagogical problems, independent educational process manages. All this is the essence of creativity, work related to the purpose and character. It is known in educational activities conducted with students To achieve the goal, teachers and children to the process of cooperation must be weighed. The teacher encourages students to cooperate with him it performs the following tasks in order to attract: it should be organized in a team in order to create cooperation The activity is interesting for the students, the age of the students should correspond to characteristics and interests; When engaging students in a task, the teacher tells them Pedagogically and psychologically correct assignment, guidance must show; when students start to do the task the teacher is both a participant and a consultant at the same time fulfills its function. At the same time, there is communication, which is the most important structural tool in a person's lifestyle in all types of professional activity. However, a number of professions in owners (actor, pedagogue, doctor, artist, etc.) it is professional not just a simple factor accompanying the activity, but professional significance it is considered an important category that forms its basis. This communication is not the usual form of interaction between people, rather, a category that ensures the success of professional activity is available as The most important thing for a pedagogue is: pedagogic technique - the teacher's role not only in the educational process, but general pedagogical knowledge necessary in all professional activities and is a set of skills. A modern teacher is a pedagogue in the system of pedagogical skills considers the role of technology to be incomparable. Because he gave his body to the

teacherability to hold (mimic, pantomimic), feelings (emotion)management, enthusiasm, skills, acquisition of speech techniques and themin educational activities, extracurricular educational and educational activities explains how to use it in the process.

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